

Review article

Neopterin and Midregional-Pro-Adrenomedullin in Veterinary Medicine

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Abstract

Today, new searches have been made both in the field of human medicine and in the field of veterinary medicine in terms of the recognition of diseases and the evaluation of prognosis. Therefore, biomarkers, which are diagnostic and more reliable prognostic indicators in the coming years, have started to be used widely today. Biomarkers are biological indicators that can show fluctuations or changes in disease and health status. At the same time, they are key biological molecules that show the change of physiological process in the face of pathological conditions. Recently, neopterin and midregional-pro-adrenomedullin have been studied as biomarkers in calves with sepsis, both diagnostically and prognostically. As a result, we believe that the use of biomarkers in the early diagnosis of diseases is important in terms of increasing the survival rate. Biomarkers provide important information about the course of the disease as prognostic.

Keywords: Biomarker, Midregional-Pro-Adrenomedullin, Neopterin

Introduction

Today, new searches have been made both in the field of human medicine and in the field of veterinary medicine in terms of the recognition of diseases and the evaluation of prognosis. Therefore, biomarkers, which are diagnostic and more reliable prognostic indicators in the coming years, have started to be used widely today. Biomarkers are biological indicators that can show fluctuations or changes in disease and health status. At the same time, they are key biological molecules that show the change of physiological process in the face of pathological conditions (De Loor et al. 2013, Köse and Maden 2013, Akyüz and Gökce 2020). The term biomarker was first mentioned in the US National Academy of Sciences Report in 1989. In addition, this term is used by important organizations such as WHO (World Health Office, World Health Organization),

AGIT (Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe) (Akay, 2004; Hewitt et al., 2004), National Cancer Institute (NCI) (Henry, 2010; Mobasherri and Cassidy, 2010; De Loor et al., 2013; Köse and Maden, 2013). Recently, biological molecules called biomarkers have been frequently used in the diagnosis of diseases, evaluation of response to treatment and evaluation of prognosis (Marshall et al., 2003; Bachmann et al., 2005). These include acute phase proteins, cytokines/chemokines, vasodilators, biomarkers related to organ failure, vascular damage biomarkers, cell surface biomarkers, coagulation biomarkers, receptor biomarkers and lactate (Dupuy et al., 2013; Meisner, 2005). Molecules that provide information about biological and pathological conditions that can be found and measured in body fluids and used to evaluate the response to treatment are

called biomarkers (Henry, 2010; Mobasheri and Cassidy, 2010; Dupuy et al., 2013; De Loor et al., 2013). Biochemical stability and work even in small blood volumes (Bossuyt et al., 2003), being able to be detected quickly, cheaply and simply (Bachmann et al., 2005), sensitivity $\approx 100\%$ and specificity $>85\%$ (Meisner, 2005) Being able to distinguish the responsible bacterial and viral pathogen (Marshall et al., 2003), distinguishing sepsis and noninfectious systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS), and providing information about the prognosis and course of treatment are the desired features of an ideal biomarker. System-specific, easy to interpret, disease-specific, and levels compatible with the stages of the disease are among the other desirable features of an ideal biomarker (Mutlu et al., 2002; Aronson, 2005; Moore et al., 2007; Tesch, 2010; Köse and Maden, 2013). Studies in the field of public health, evaluation of the effects of some chemical and biological substances on the organism and sensitivity to them, determining the response and prognosis to treatment in clinics and revealing risky situations, if necessary, directing the treatment constitute the field of use of biomarkers (Akay, 2004; Diamandis, 2004; Tesch, 2010).

Neopterin

Neopterin finds use in the medical field to help diagnose bacterial and viral infections in general. It is mostly released by cytokines stimulated in inflammatory conditions. Although it is widely used in human medicine to provide information about the prognosis of diseases like other biomarkers, its use in veterinary medicine is limited. Plasma neopterin concentration is actually an indicator of circulating active monocytes and macrophage activation. Neopterin plasma concentration variation can be considered as a direct reflection of the activation of monocytes and macrophages against the disease (Brunkhorst et al., 1999, Ruokonen et al., 2002). Neopterin is a metabolic compound of guanosine triphosphate, which chemically belongs to the pteridine group. It is released from macrophages and dendritic cells stimulated by cytokines (Michalak et al., 2017, Pergialiotis et al., 2018, Akyuz and Gökce 2021).

Midregional-Pro-Adrenomedullin

Adrenomedullin (ADM) is an important biomarker in the evaluation of the prognosis of patients (Rey et al., 2013). ADM was first measured with the radioimmunoassay (RIA) method in 1993 and its effects on the circulatory system were expressed (Kalman, 2002). Its precursor is Prepro-ADM. Pro-ADM is synthesized from Prepro-ADM. ADM is synthesized from

Pro-ADM (Morgenthaler et al., 2005). This process is encoded by mRNA (Garazzino et al., 2019). Adrenomedullin is 27% similar to calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP) (Geven et al., 2018) and is produced and released during sepsis (Jordan et al., 2014). ADM consists of thalamus and hypothalamus, adipose tissue, adrenal cortex, bone tissue (Valenzuela-Sanchez et al., 2016), heart, vascular smooth muscle cells (Gille et al., 2017), adrenal medulla, lung, kidney, central nervous system, it is released from gastrointestinal tissues (Garazzino et al., 2019). In addition, it is also produced from monocytes and macrophages (Geven et al., 2018). Vasodilator (Akpınar et al., 2014), diuretic and natriuretic (Rey et al., 2013) positive inotropic, antifibrotic, antioxidant and angiogenesis, insulin secretion inhibitor, aldosterone inhibitor (Peacock, 2014), bronchodilator (Önal et al., 2018) and adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) inhibitor (Valenzuela-Sanchez et al., 2016). In addition, it has antimicrobial (Garazzino et al., 2019), antifungal and anti-inflammatory (Akpınar et al., 2014) effects (Bernal-Morell et al., 2018). The presence of adrenomedullin on the epithelial surfaces of the respiratory, digestive and urogenital systems shows that it plays a role in the body's defense (Valenzuela-Sanchez et al., 2016). ADM is bound to a protein called ADM-binding protein 1 (AMBP-1). Proinflammatory cytokines such as angiotensin-II (A-II), bradykinin, noradrenaline, endothelin-1 (ET-1), adrenaline, glucocorticoid and thyroid hormones, lipopolysaccharides (Garayoa et al., 2000) TNF- and IL-1 (Ghobrial et al., 2000) and conditions such as hypoxia, oxidative stress and inflammation increase ADM synthesis (Garazzino et al., 2019). Adrenomedullin sepsis (Geven et al., 2018) serves as a good biomarker in circulatory and respiratory system diseases. In such cases, ADM plasma levels increase (Morgenthaler et al., 2005; Bernal-Morell et al., 2018). Since ADM is rapidly metabolized (Miguel et al., 2011), its half-life is short (Abd Elmoutaleb et al., 2016). For this reason, the stable middle region fragment called Pro-ADM is measured (Sönmezer and Tülek, 2015). MR-Pro-ADM is used in the evaluation of prognosis in patients with sepsis (Valenzuela-Sanchez et al., 2015). -Ribalta et al., 2020) and its sensitivity is 91.6% and its specificity is 87.4% (Abd Elmoutaleb et al., 2016).

Neopterin and Midregional-Pro-Adrenomedullin in Calves with Neonatal Sepsis

Recently, biomarkers have been used frequently, especially in sepsis. The inflammatory response of the organism during infection is a clinical syndrome and is called sepsis. In case of sepsis, morbidity and mor-

tality rates are high. Therefore, early diagnosis and initiation of treatment are very important. Generally, bacterial infections play a role in the etiology of sepsis. Culture methods are frequently used in the diagnosis of bacterial infections. However, because this method takes some time, treatment is delayed (Bachmann et al., 2005; Dupuy et al., 2013). In the case of sepsis, the release of biomarkers occurs as a result of the interaction between the organism and the pathogen (Bonza et al., 2005). In a study conducted in calves with neonatal sepsis, it was determined that the neopterin concentration decreased in parallel with the treatment at certain hourly intervals. It has been reported to be both diagnostic and prognostic in the evaluation of calves with sepsis (Akyuz and Gokce, 2021). In a similar study, it was determined that ADM is especially important in the diagnosis of calves with neonatal sepsis (Sezer and Gokce 2021).

Conclusion

As a result, we believe that the use of biomarkers in the early diagnosis of diseases is important in terms of increasing the survival rate.

References

Abd Elmoutaleb, A.T., Aly, H.A., Bayomy, E.M., Abdelhamed, M.R., Esmael, N.F. (2016). Plasma procalcitonin and proadrenomedullin concentrations as predictive markers for early onset neonatal sepsis. *American Journal of Biochemistry and Biotechnology*, 6(1), 6-15.

Akay, C. (2004). Biomarkörlerin toksikolojide kullanımı. *Gülhane Tıp Dergisi*, 46 (1), 73 – 83.

Akyüz, E., Gökce, G (2021). Neopterin, procalcitonin, clinical biochemistry, and hematology in calves with neonatal sepsis. *Trop Anim Health Prod* 53, 354. Doi: 10.1007/s11250-021-02779-z

Akpınar, S., Rollas, K., Alagöz, A., Seğmen, F., Sıpit, T. (2014). Performance evaluation of MR-proadrenomedullin and other scoring systems in severe sepsis with pneumonia. *Journal of Thoracic Disease*, 6(7), 921-929. doi: 10.3978/j.issn.2072-1439.2014.06.42.

Akyüz E., Gökce G. (2020). Investigations on neopterin, procalcitonin, clinical biochemistry and hematology in neonatal sepsis suspicious calves (PhD Thesis), Kafkas University, Health Sciences Institute, Kars, Turkey.

Aronson, J.K. (2005). Biomarkers and surrogate endpoints. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 59, 491-494. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2125.2005.02435.x.

Bachmann, L.M., Juni, P., Reichenbach, S., Ziswiler, H.R., Kessels, A.G., Vogelin, E. (2005). Consequences of different diagnostic “gold standards” in test accuracy research: Carpal Tunnel Syndrome as an example. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 34(4), 953-955. doi: 10.1093/ije/dyi105.

Bernal-Morell, E., García-Villalba, E., del Carmen Vera, M., Medina, B., Martínez, M., Callejo, V., Valero, S., Cinesi, C., Piñera, P., Alcaraz, A., Marin, I., Muñoz, A., Cano, A. (2018). Usefulness of midregional pro-adrenomedullin as a marker of organ damage and predictor of mortality in patients with sepsis. *Journal of Infection*, 76(3), 249-257. doi: 10.1016/j.jinf.2017.12.003.

Bossuyt, P.M., Reitsma, J.B., Bruns, D.E., Gatsonis, C.A., Glasziou, P.P., Irwig, L.M., Moher, D., Rennie, D., de Vet, H.C.W., Lijmer, J.G. (2003). Standards for reporting of diagnostic accuracy. The STARD statement for reporting studies of diagnostic accuracy: explanation and elaboration. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 138(1), W1-12. doi: 10.7326/0003-4819-138-1-200301070-00012-w1.

Bozza, F.A., Bozza, P.T., Castro Faria Neto, H.C. (2005). Beyond sepsis pathophysiology with cytokines: what is their value as biomarkers for disease severity? *Memórias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz*, 100(Suppl. 1), 217-21. doi: 10.1590/s0074-02762005000900037.

Brunkhorst, F.M., Eberhard, O.K., Brunkhorst, R. (1999). Discrimination of infectious and noninfectious causes of early acute respiratory distress syndrome by procalcitonin. *Crit Care Med* 27: 2172-2176. doi: 10.1097/00003246-199910000-00016

Cho, S.Y., Choi, H.J. (2014). Biomarkers of sepsis. *Infection & Chemotherapy*, 46(1), 1-12. doi: 10.3947/ic.2014.46.1.1.

De Loor, J., Daminet, S., Smets, P., Maddens, B., Meyer, E. (2013). Urinary biomarkers for acute kidney injury in dogs. *Journal of veterinary internal medicine*, 27, 998-1010. doi: 10.1111/jvim.12155.

Diamandis, E.P. (2004). How are we going to discover new cancer biomarkers? A proteomic approach for bladder cancer. *Clinical Chemistry*, 50(5), 793-795. doi: 10.1373/clinchem.2004.032177.

Dupuy, A.M., Philippart, F., Pean Y, Lasocki, S., Charles, P.E., Chalumeau, M., Claessens, Y.E., Quenot, J.P., Gras-Le Guen, C., Ruiz, S., Luyt, C.E., Roche, N., Stahl, J.P., Bedos, J.P., Pugin, J., Gauzit, R., Misset, B., Brun-Buisson, C., Rapin, M. (2013). Role of biomarkers in the management of antibiotic

therapy: an expert panel review: I- currently available biomarkers for clinical use in acute infections. *Annals of Intensive Care*, 3(1), 22. doi: 10.1186/2110-5820-3-22.

Garayoa, M., Martinez, A., Lee, S., Pio, R., An, W.G., Neckers, L., Trepel, J., Montuenga, L.M., Ryan, H., Johnson, R., Gassmann, M., Cuttitta, F. (2000). Hypoxia-inducible factor-1 (HIF-1) up-regulates adrenomedullin expression in human tumor cell lines during oxygen deprivation: A possible promotion mechanism of carcinogenesis. *Molecular Endocrinology*, 14(6), 848-862. doi: 10.1210/mend.14.6.0473.

Garazzino, S., Altieri, E., Denina, M. (2019). The role of Pro-adrenomedullin as a marker of severe bacterial infection in children: A Review. *Reports*, 2:17.

Geven, C., Kox, M., Pickkers, P. (2018). Adrenomedullin and Adrenomedullin- targeted therapy as treatment strategies relevant for sepsis. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 9, 292. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2018.00292.

Ghobrial, E.E., Khorshied, M.M., Adly, S.B., Aziz, M.M. (2020). Proadrenomedullin as a prognostic biomarker for critically-ill septic children. *Res Square*, 1:15.

Gille, J., Ostermann, H., Dragu, A., Sablotzki, A. (2017). MR-proADM: A new biomarker for early diagnosis of sepsis in burned patients. *Journal of Burn Care & Research*, 38, 290-298. doi: 10.1097/BCR.0000000000000508.

Henry, C.J. (2010). Biomarkers in veterinary cancer screening: Applications, limitations and expectations. *The Veterinary Journal*, 185, 10–14. doi: 10.1016/j.tvjl.2010.04.005.

Hewitt, S.M., Dear, J., Star, R.A. (2004). Discovery of protein biomarkers for renal diseases. *American Society of Nephrology*, 15, 1677–1689. Doi: 10.1097/01.asn.0000129114.92265.32

Jordan, I., Corniero, P., Balaguer, M., Ortiz, J., Vila, D., Velasco, J., Cambra, F.J., Esteban, E. (2014). Adrenomedullin is a useful biomarker for the prognosis of critically ill septic children. *Biomark Med*, 8(9) 1065-1072. doi: 10.2217/bmm.14.77.

Kalman, S. (2002). Adrenomedullin: Yeni bir renal düzenleyici peptid. *Turkish Journal of Nephrology*, 11(4), 198-201.

Köse, S.I., Maden, M. (2013). Biyomarkerlar ve Klinik Kullanımları. *Dicle Üniversitesi Veteriner Fakültesi Dergisi*, 2(1), 1-8.

Marshall, J.C., Vincent, J.L., Fink, M.P., Cook,

D.J., Rubenfeld, G., Foster, D., Fisher, C.J., Faist, E., Reinhart, K. (2003). Measures, markers, and mediators: toward a staging system for clinical sepsis. A report of the Fifth Toronto Sepsis Roundtable, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, October 25-26, 2000. *Critical Care Medicine*, 31(5), 1560-1567. 10.1097/01.CCM.0000065186.67848.3A.

Meisner, M. (2005). Biomarkers of sepsis: clinically useful? *Current Opinion in Critical Care*, 11(5), 473-80. doi: 10.1097/01.ccx.0000176694.92883.ce.

Michalak, L., Bulska, M., Strzabala, K., Szczesniak, P (2017). Neopterin as a marker of cellular immunological response. *Postepy Hig Med Dosw (Online)*, 71(1): 727-736. doi: 10.5604/01.3001.0010.3851

Miguel, D., Prieto, B., Costa, M., Coto, D., Alvarez, F.V. (2011). Cord blood plasma reference intervals for potential sepsis markers: Pro-adrenomedullin, pro-endothelin, and pro atrial natriuretic peptide. *Clinical Biochemistry*, 44, 337-341. doi: 10.1016/j.clinbiochem.2010.12.012.

Mobasheri, A., Cassidy, J.P. (2010). Biomarkers in veterinary medicine: Towards targeted, individualised therapies for companion animals. *The Veterinary Journal*, 185, 1–3. doi: 10.1016/j.tvjl.2010.04.003.

Moore, R.E., Kirwan, J., Doherty, M.K., Whitfield, P.D. (2007). Biomarker discovery in animal health and disease: The application of post-genomic technologies. *Biomark Insights*, 2, 185–196.

Morgenthaler, N.G., Struck, J., Alonso, C., Bergmann, A. (2005). Measurement of Midregional Pro-adrenomedullin in plasma with an immunoluminometric assay. *Clinical Chemistry*, 51(10), 1823-1829. doi: 10.1373/clinchem.2005.051110.

Mutlu, N., Türkeri, L., Emerk, K. (2002). Mesane kanseri tanı ve izleminde yeni bir tümör belirteci “Mesane Kanseri Fibronektin” (BTF)’in analitik ve klinik değerlendirilmesi. *Türk Üroloji Dergisi*, 28(4), 390-397.

Önal, U., Valenzuela-Sánchez, F., Vandana, K.E., Rello, J. (2018). Mid-Regional Pro Adrenomedullin (MR-proADM) as a biomarker for sepsis and septic shock: Narrative review. *Healthcare*, 6(3), 110. doi: 10.3390/healthcare6030110.

Peacock, W.F. (2014). Novel biomarkers in acute heart failure: Mr-pro-adrenomedullin. *Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine*, 52(10), 1433-1435. doi: 10.1515/cclm-2014-0222.

Pergialiotis, V., Karampetsou, N., Zoumpourlis, P., Papantoniou, N., Thomakos, N., Daskalakis, G (2018). Serum neopterin levels in women with preeclampsia: A systematic review. *Hypertens Pregnancy*, 37(4): 220-226. doi: 10.1080/10641955.2018.1526300

Ruokonen, E., Iikka, L., Niskanen, M., Takala, J. (2002). Procalcitonin and neopterin as indicators of infection in critically ill patients. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand* 46: 398-404. doi: 10.1034/j.1399-6576.2002.460412.x

Rey, C., García-Hernández, I., Concha, A., Martínez-Cambor, P., Botrán, M., Medina, A., Prieto, B., López-Herce, J. (2013). Pro-adrenomedullin, pro-endothelin-1, procalcitonin, C-reactive protein and mortality risk in critically ill children: A prospective study. *Critical Care*, 17, R240. doi: 10.1186/cc13064.

Sezer, M., Gökce, G., (2021). Sepsis Süpheli buzağlarda Strem-1, MR-PRO-Adrenomedullin (MR-Pro-ADM), klinik biyokimya ve hematoloji üzerine araştırmalar. Kafkas Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, (Doktora Tezi), Kars, Türkiye.

Sole-Ribalta, A., Bobillo-Pérez, S., Valls, A., Girna-Alarcón, M., Launes, C., Cambra, F.J., Jordan, I., Esteban, E. (2020). Diagnostic and prognostic value of procalcitonin and mid-regional pro-adrenomedullin in septic paediatric patients. *European Journal of Pediatrics*, 179 (7), 1089-1096. doi: 10.1007/s00431-020-03587-7.

Sönmezer, M.Ç., Tülek, N. (2015). Bakteriyel infeksiyonlarda ve sepsiste biyobelirteçler. *Klinik Dergisi*, 28(3), 96-102.

Tesch, G.H. (2010). Serum and urine biomarkers of kidney disease: A pathophysiological perspective. *Nephrology*, 15 (6), 609-616. doi: 10.1111/j.1440-1797.2010.01361.x

Valenzuela Sanchez, F., Valenzuela Méndez, B., Bohollo de Austria, R., Gutierrez, J.F.R., Franco, M.J., García, M.A.G., Chaumel, A.J. (2015). Diagnostic and prognostic usefulness of mid-regional pro-adrenomedullin levels in patients with severe sepsis. *Intensive Care Medicine Experimental*, 3 (Suppl 1), A306.

Valenzuela-Sánchez, F., Valenzuela-Méndez, B., Rodríguez-Gutiérrez, J.F., Estella-García, Á., González-García, M.Á. (2016). New role of biomarkers: Mid-regional pro-adrenomedullin, the biomarker of organ failure. *The Annals of Translational Medicine*'s, 4(17), 329. doi: 10.21037/atm.2016.08.65.